

Appendix A — Student-Designed Question Instrument (Full List)

The following 25 questions were designed by the Erdkinder students before the visit. Usage status is recorded from the Section 3 Question Tracker.

#	Question	Asked?	Category
1	How did you come up with this idea?	Yes	Origin
2	How long has it been since you started?	Yes	Origin
3	How did you execute this?	No	Business mechanics
4	How do you sell your products?	Yes	Business mechanics
5	How do you feel when you bake?	Yes	Emotional/experiential
6	What else do you do other than cooking and baking?	Yes	Experiential
7	What was your biggest order?	Yes	Business mechanics
8	Who helped you come up with this idea?	Yes	Origin
9	How did you learn to bake and cook?	Yes	Developmental
10	What is your best seller item?	No	Business mechanics
11	Who is the best chef among you all?	No	Relational/hierarchy
12	What is your favourite recipe?	No	Emotional/experiential
13	What inspired you to do this?	No	Origin/motivation
14	What is your least sold product?	No	Business mechanics
15	Are you working on new recipes?	No	Developmental
16	What do you enjoy about cooking and baking?	No	Emotional/experiential
17	What is your least favourite recipe?	No	Comparative/relational
18	Which recipe takes the longest to make?	No	Business mechanics
19	Which recipe is the quickest?	No	Business mechanics
20	Did you think of starting a restaurant?	Yes	Future/developmental
21	What is the latest recipe you have tried?	No	Developmental
22	What was the first recipe you tried?	No	Developmental
23	How long does it take to give a meal after customers order?	Yes	Business mechanics
24	When do you take holiday?	No	Work-life/relational
25	Do all of you work at once or in batches?	No	Operations

